

MEDICAL SCIENCES

BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM FEMALE PATIENTS WITH URINARY TRACT INFECTION AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE DISTRIBUTION: INTEGRATED MEDICINE APPROACH TO INFECTION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are one of the most common infectious diseases in the community. The ongoing misuse of antimicrobials has led to the rise of bacterial resistance, a worldwide problem. The aim of this study was to examine the distribution and antibiotic resistance profiles of pathogens commonly found in female patients with urinary tract infections and to provide potential benefits of integrative treatment strategies. The study was conducted on female patients diagnosed with urinary tract infection who applied to the "Bioloji Tababat" clinic in Baku between June 2023 and July 2024. Etiological profiles and antibiotic resistance rates of bacteria ranked according to different age categories were analyzed. The study included 233 female patients with clinical urinary tract infection. Of these, 165 (70.8%) were positive for gram-negative bacteria and 68 (29.2%) were positive for gram-positive bacteria only for *Staphylococcus aureus*. The most common gram-negative uropathogen was *E. coli* (n = 114; 48.9). *E. coli* showed higher susceptibility to meropenem (96.5%), amikacin (99.1%), tobramycin (98.2%), nitrofurantoin (96.5%) and piperacillin/tazobactam (98.2%). The highest resistance rate of *K. pneumoniae* was detected against ampicillin and imipenem (100%). *S. aureus* was most susceptible to nitrofurantoin (97.1%) and tigecycline (98.6%). The highest number of *E. coli* was found in the 19-29 age group (60.5%, 69/114), followed by the 0-18 (12.2%, 14/114) and ≥60 age groups (12.2%, 14/114). The second most common organism in the 19-29 age group was *S. aureus* 58.8% (40/68), followed by *K. pneumoniae* 55.5% (10/18). A significant association was found between the 0-18, 19-29, 30-39 and ≥60 age groups in terms of bacterial isolates (p < 0.05). The results of the study highlight the challenges of antibiotic resistance in the treatment of UTI and the potential contribution of integrative treatment approaches to this process.

Keywords: urinary tract infection, antimicrobial resistance, female

INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are among the most common bacterial infections worldwide and are particularly common in women. Although the clinical symptoms of UTIs are heterogeneous, most UTIs are usually treated empirically. Bacteria are the main causative agents of these infections, but more rarely, other microorganisms such as fungi and some viruses have also been reported to be responsible for UTIs (Mancuso, Giuseppe, et al., 2023). The etiology of urinary tract infections is thought to be predictable because of the relatively constant spectrum of pathogens involved, but with improvements in medical interventions, pharmacotherapy and increasing numbers of patients affected by immunosuppression (disease-related or iatrogenic), other less common pathogens are now emerging as prominent drivers of disease (Gajdács, Márió, et al., 2020).

Among the commonly isolated uropathogens, *Escherichia coli* is the most common bacterium in both community and hospital infections (75-90% isolates), followed by other pathogenic microorganisms such as *Proteus mirabilis*, *Staphylococcus saprophyticus* (especially frequently isolated from young women), *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and

Pseudomonas aeruginosa. (Fazly Bazzaz, Bibi Sedigheh, et al., 2021). *Non-E. coli microorganisms are more prevalent, especially in immunocompromised patients and those with a urinary catheter prior to hospital admission* (Medina-Polo, Jose, Kurt G. Naber, and Truls E., 2021).

The spread and emergence of multidrug-resistant organisms is a global public health problem. In addition, the incidence of UTIs due to multidrug resistance (MDR) is increasing. This is particularly causing a significant increase in the spread of antibiotic resistance and the economic burden of these infections (Mahony, Michelle, et al., 2020). Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) enzymes have spread in part due to the transmission of mobile genetic elements between bacteria, and ESBL-producing bacteria are frequently identified. Furthermore, isolation of multidrug-resistant microorganisms is more common in immunocompromised patients, those with previous urinary tract infections, and those with upper urinary tract urinary catheters (Medina-Polo, Jose, Kurt G. Naber, and Truls E., 2021).

Urinary tract infections are generally classified as lower or upper and complicated or uncomplicated urinary tract infections depending on the site of

infection and the patient's body condition. Upper urinary tract infections affect the kidneys and ureters as in the case of pyelonephritis, while lower urinary tract infections affect the urethra and bladder. Also, uncomplicated urinary tract infections are urinary tract infections that do not have any functional or anatomical abnormalities. Complicated urinary tract infections, on the other hand, are all cases other than uncomplicated urinary tract infections (Kaur, Rajanbir, and Rajinder Kaur., 2021).

Urine specimens are one of the most frequently submitted specimens for culture in the clinical microbiology laboratory, outnumbering most other specimen types. The epidemiology, species distribution, and susceptibility patterns of uropathogens vary widely geographically and temporally, and are also strongly related to the reported patient population. There is increasing demand for further research to develop diagnostic and therapeutic options and improve patient care (Behzadi, Payam, et al., 2021; Abraham, O., 2016). An approach based solely on antibiotic treatment no longer seems sufficient in the treatment of UTI. In order to effectively manage UTI, integrative treatment methods that support the immune system and reduce inflammation are becoming increasingly important in addition to antibiotic treatment (Stapleton, A. E., 2016). Integrative therapy includes a variety of approaches, including probiotics, anti-inflammatory dietary supplements, herbal treatments (phytotherapy), and immune system boosters. These approaches may have a potential impact not only in treating UTIs but also in reducing the development of resistance (Aggarwal, Nishant, Stephen Leslie, and Saran Lotfollahzadeh., 2024).

Evaluating the effects of integrative approaches in addition to conventional antibiotic therapy in the management of urinary tract infections constitutes an important area of research in terms of both controlling the development of resistance and supporting the general well-being of patients. The aim of this study was to examine the distribution and antibiotic resistance profiles of pathogens commonly found in female patients with urinary tract infections and to provide potential benefits of integrative treatment strategies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

The study was conducted on 233 female patients aged 1-85 years who were diagnosed with urinary tract infection and applied to a private clinic in Baku between June 2023-July 2024. Patient files were reviewed and demographic characteristics, symptoms, physical examination findings, laboratory values, and treatment choices were evaluated.

Bacterial Culture

Midstream urine samples were collected from all patients included in the study under sterile conditions and processed within 2 hours of collection. Urine samples sent to the laboratory were cultured on 5% sheep blood agar and Eosin-Methylene Blue (EMB) agar media using a graduated loop (0.01cc). The bacteria were incubated for 18-24 hours to multiply. After the allotted time period, the culture plates were evaluated for the presence of bacterial colonies. They were reported as significant or insignificant growth by the colony counting method. The colony count method is a technique by which the number of viable bacterial colonies per millilitre of urine sample can be counted numerically, a quantitative measurement by which we can distinguish true bacteriuria from bacterial contamination, which usually occurs during improper collection of midstream urine. Only urine samples with growth of 10^5 CFU/ml (colony forming unit) were included in the study. In the presence of growth, various ancillary tests (Gram stain, catalase, oxidase, coagulase, lactose fermentation, urea test, indole test, motility medium etc.) were performed for identification. These urine samples were also centrifuged and used for direct microscopic examination of urine sediment, red blood cells (RBCs), leukocytes, epithelial cells, casts, crystals and parasites.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Tests

Identification of bacteria isolated from urine samples and antibiotic susceptibility tests were performed manually. Antimicrobial susceptibility of isolates was evaluated using disk diffusion technique. The surface of Mueller-Hinton agar was uniformly covered with standard inoculum (Fisher Scientific, USA) adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard turbidity. Antibiograms were performed by Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method using antibiotic-impregnated disks recommended by the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST). Antibiogram results were generally reported as susceptible, intermediate or resistant. ESBL-producing strains were identified using double-disk synergy test.

Statistical analysis

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 30.0 program was used for statistical analysis and analyzed with the Chi-square test. A p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study included 233 female patients with clinical urinary tract infections. Of these, 165 (70.8%) were positive for gram-negative bacteria and 68 (29.2%) were positive for gram-positive bacteria only for *Staphylococcus aureus*. The results showed that *E. coli* was the most common gram-negative uropathogen ($n = 114$; 48.9%), followed by *K. pneumoniae* ($n = 18$; 7.7%), with the lowest rate belonging to *E. cloacae* ($n = 4$; 1.7%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Prevalence of bacteria isolated from urine samples of women with urinary tract infections.

E. coli showed higher susceptibility to meropenem (96.5%), amikacin (99.1%), tobramycin (98.2%), nitrofurantoin (96.5%) and piperacillin/tazobactam (98.2%), followed by cefoxitin (92.9%), fosfomicin (91.3%), gentamicin (89.8%), ciprofloxacin (87.8%), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (72%), cefepime (66.7%), cefotaxime (66.7%), cefuroxime (57.1%), cefixime (61.5%), imipenem (6.2%). The highest resistance rate was against ampicillin (100%) and amoxicillin clavulanic acid (99.1%) (Table 1).

K. pneumoniae was most susceptible to tobramycin and piperacillin/tazobactam (100%), followed by amikacin and nitrofurantoin (94.5%), gentamicin and meropenem (88.5%), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (83.4%), ciprofloxacin, cefixime, cefepime, cefotaxime, cefuroxime, cefixime, fosfomicin (77.8%) and cefoxitin (72.3%), while the highest resistance rate was detected against ampicillin and imipenem (100%).

Proteus spp. was most susceptible to amikacin and tobramycin (100%), while it was reported to be highly resistant to imipenem and ampicillin (100%). Gentamicin and piperacillin/tazobactam (85.8%), cefepime, cefuroxime, cefotaxime, cefixime, cefoxitin, meropenem,

fosfomicin (71.5%), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and ciprofloxacin (57.2%), amoxicillin clavulanic acid (42.9%), nitrofurantoin (28.6%) were detected.

K. oxytoca was highly susceptible to meropenem, amikacin, tobramycin and fosfomicin (100%), *Klebsiella aerogenes* was highly susceptible to gentamicin and tobramycin (100%), while both bacteria were highly resistant to ampicillin (100%).

E. cloacae was found to be highly susceptible to amikacin, tobramycin, gentamicin, meropenem, ciprofloxacin (100%). The highest resistance rate was reported against ampicillin and imipenem (100%). *P. aeruginosa* showed the highest susceptibility to amikacin and tobramycin (100%).

S. aureus was most susceptible to nitrofurantoin (97.1%) and tigecycline (98.6%), followed by moxifloxacin (95.6%), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and tobramycin (89.8%), linezolid (85.3%), amikacin and levofloxacin (82.4%), and gentamicin (80.9%). The highest resistance rate was detected against penicillin (75%) (Table 1).

Table 1.

Comparison of antibiotic resistance rates of uropathogens isolated from urine samples

Antibiotics	<i>E. coli</i> n=114	<i>Proteus spp.</i> n=7	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> n=18	<i>E. cloacae</i> n=4	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> n=8	<i>K. oxytoca</i> n=9	<i>K. aerogenes</i> n=5	<i>S. aureus</i> n=68
Amikacin	1 (0,87%)	0	1 (5,5%)	0	0	0	1 (20%)	12 (17,6%)
Gentamycin	9 (10,2%)	1 (14,2%)	2 (11,1%)	0	NT	1 (11,1%)	0	13 (19,1%)
Tobramycin	2 (1,75%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	7 (10,2%)
Ampicillin	114 (100%)	7 (100%)	18 (100%)	4 (100%)	NT	9 (100%)	5 (100%)	NT
Amoxy-clav	113 (99,1%)	4 (57,1%)	16 (88,8%)	3 (75%)	NT	8 (88,8%)	4 (80%)	NT
Piperacillin-tazobactam	2 (1,75%)	1 (14,2%)	0	1 (25%)	3 (37,5%)	2 (22,2%)	1 (20%)	NT

Cefepime	38 (33,3%)	2 (1,75%)	4 (22,2%)	2 (50%)	4 (50%)	6 (66,6%)	1 (20%)	NT
Cefotaxime	38 (33,3%)	2 (1,75%)	4 (22,2%)	2 (50%)	NT	6 (66,6%)	1 (20%)	NT
Cefuroxime	49 (42,9%)	2 (1,75%)	4 (22,2%)	2 (50%)	NT	6 (66,6%)	1 (20%)	NT
Cefixime	44 (38,5%)	2 (1,75%)	4 (22,2%)	3 (75%)	NT	6 (66,6%)	1 (20%)	NT
Co-trimoxazole	32 (28%)	3 (42,8%)	3 (16,6%)	1 (25%)	NT	5 (55,5%)	4 (80%)	7 (10,2%)
Imipenem	107 (93,8%)	7 (100%)	18 (100%)	4 (100%)	5 (62,5%)	8 (88,8%)	5 (100%)	NT
Meropenem	4 (3,5%)	2 (1,75%)	2 (11,1%)	0	3 (37,5)	0	1 (20%)	NT
Fosfomicin	10 (8,7%)	2 (1,75%)	4 (22,2%)	2 (50%)	NT	0	2 (40%)	NT
Nitrofurantoin	4 (3,5%)	5 (71,4%)	1 (5,5%)	1 (25%)	NT	1 (11,1%)	2 (40%)	NT
Penicillin	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	51 (75%)
Cefoxitin	97 (7,89%)	2 (1,75%)	5 (27,7%)	1 (25%)	NT	1 (11,1%)	3 (60%)	18 (26,4%)
Ciprofloxacin	14 (12,2%)	3 (42,8%)	4 (22,2%)	0	1	1 (11,1%)	1 (20%)	14 (20,5%)
Tigecycline	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	1 (1,4%)
Moxifloxacin	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	3 (4,4%)
Tetracycline	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	21 (30,8%)
Levofloxacin	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	12 (17,6%)
Linezolid	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	10 (14,7%)
Rifampicin	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	19 (27,9%)

NT-not tested

When Enterobacteriaceae were compared with ESBL production, it was observed that ESBL negative strains were detected at a higher rate than positive

strains. The difference was found to be statistically significant for *E. coli*, *K. oxytoca*, but not for other bacteria (Table 2).

Table 2.

Frequency of ESBL-producing and non-ESBL-producing enterobacteria.

Bakteriler	ESBL producer	Non- ESBL producer	P value
<i>E.coli</i>	43 (37,7%)	71 (62,3%)	0,000
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	1 (14,2%)	6 (85,8%)	0.058
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	11 (61,1%)	7 (38,9%)	0.018
<i>E. cloacae</i>	0 (0)	4(100%)	0.135
<i>K. oxytoca</i>	4 (44,4%)	5 (55,6%)	0.073
<i>K. aerogenes</i>	2 (40%)	3 (60%)	0.65

The highest number of *E. coli* was found in the 19-29 age group (60.5%, 69/114), followed by the 0-18 (12.2%, 14/114) and ≥ 60 age groups (12.2%, 14/114). The second most common organism in the 19-29 age group was *S. aureus* 58.8% (40/68), followed by *K. pneumoniae* 55.5% (10/18). *P. aeruginosa* was detected at the highest rate in the 19-29 age group, but was not

detected in the 0-18, 50-59, ≥ 60 age groups. *K. oxytoca* and *Proteus spp.* were detected at the rate of 33.3% in the 0-18 and 19-29 age groups, but were not detected in the 40-49 age group. A significant relationship was found between the 0-18, 19-29, 30-39 and ≥ 60 age groups in terms of bacterial isolates ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3.

Bacterial distribution of the study population according to age groups.

Age	<i>E.coli</i> n=114	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> n=18	<i>K. oxytoca</i> n=9	<i>Proteus spp</i> n=7	<i>K. aerogenes</i> n=5	<i>E. cloacae</i> n=4	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> n=8	<i>S.aureus</i> n=68	P value
0-18	14(12,2%)	2(11,1%)	3(33,3%)	3(42,8%)	0	0	0	8(11,7%)	0,000
19-29	69(60,5%)	10(55,5%)	3(33,3%)	3(42,8%)	3(60%)	1(25%)	6(75%)	40(58,8%)	0,000
30-39	11(9,6%)	2(11,1%)	1(11,1%)	1(14,2%)	1(20%)	2(50%)	1(12,5%)	17(25%)	0,000
40-49	3(1,6%)	0	0	0	0	1(25%)	1(12,5%)	0	0,390
50-59	2(1,75%)	1(5,55%)	1(11,1%)	1(14,2%)	0	0	0	1(147%)	1,000
≥60	14(12,2%)	3(16,6%)	1(11,1%)	1(14,2%)	1(20%)	0	0	1(147%)	0,000

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION

This study evaluates the antibiotic resistance profiles of bacterial pathogens isolated from female patients with urinary tract infections (UTIs) and the potential contribution of integrative approaches in the treatment of UTIs. Resistance to antibiotics commonly used in the treatment of UTIs causes serious problems in the management of infections. In particular, the production of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) in Gram-negative bacteria such as *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* renders many antibiotics used against these bacteria ineffective. In this context, integrative treatment approaches that go beyond conventional antibiotic therapy and aim to prevent recurrence of infection are considered as promising alternatives (Ventola, C. Lee, 2015; Al-Zahrani, J., Al Dossari, K., Gabr, A. et al., 2019).

The etiology, pathophysiology and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of uropathogens continue to change with time and space (Ahmed vd., 2019). Identification of the organism and antibiotic susceptibility is crucial to managing UTI. This exemplifies the importance of close collaboration and cooperation between the clinician and microbiologist (Moue vd., 2015).

The most common gram-negative bacteria isolated from the samples in our study was *E. coli* (48.9%). These findings are consistent with those of other published studies, where the prevalence of *E. coli* was 97.0%, 92.6%, 74.0%, 55.0%, 49.3%, 43.5%, 41.9%, and 40.0% (Arora et al., 2016; Odoki et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020; Daoud et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2022; Huang et al., 2022; Jagadeesan et al., 2022; Komagamine et al., 2022). In our study, *K. pneumoniae* (7.7%) was the second most frequently reported gram-negative bacteria, while the lowest rate was found to belong to *E. cloacae* (1.7%). The increasing prevalence of gram-negative bacteria from the Enterobacteriaceae family to cause UTI may be attributed to several factors, including adhesion to the uroepithelium due to colonization of the urogenital mucosa via adhesins, pili, fimbriae, and the P-1 blood group phenotypic receptor (Terlizzi et al., 2017).

In our study, 86.0% of the pathogens were MDR, while this rate was 91.3% in Nepal, 85.5% in Somaliland, 83.0% in Haryana, 45.1% in Tunisia and 42.6% in China. (Ben Ayed et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2022; Malik et al., 2021; Shilpakar et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2022). Inappropriate and indiscriminate use of broad-spectrum antibiotics and prolonged hospital stay are the main etiological factors associated with MDR infections (Prestinaci et al., 2015). In our study, 37.7% of *E. coli* produced ESBL, while other publications reported 25.2%; 35.7%, 46.0% and 52-67% (Gharavi et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2022; Naushad et al., 2022; Sadeghi et al., 2022).

In our study, the highest number of *E. coli* was found in the 19-29 age group (60%), followed by the 0-18 (12.2%) and ≥ 60 age groups (12.2%). In the study conducted by Bhargava, K., et al., *E. coli* was detected highest in the 18-50 age group (58.17%) (Bhargava, Kanika, et al., 2022).

The prevalence of antibiotic-resistant strains creates various challenges in the treatment of UTIs. Antibiotic resistance not only increases treatment costs, but also prolongs treatment, increases hospital stays and leads to wider health problems (McGuire, Shelley., 2015). The main reasons for the increase in antibiotic resistance include unnecessary antibiotic use, non-compliance with treatment, and widespread use of antibiotics in veterinary medicine and agriculture. In particular, incorrect or unnecessary use of antibiotics in community-acquired UTI cases is one of the main factors that accelerate the development of resistance. Studies show that uncontrolled use of antibiotics in animal husbandry and agriculture allows resistant bacterial strains to pass to humans through the environment (Gupta, K., Bhadelia, N., Walters, M. S., 2017). This shows that antibiotics threaten public health not only in terms of health but also through environmental effects.

The use of integrative approaches in combination with traditional antibiotic therapy in the treatment of UTI offers the potential for more effective management, especially against resistant bacteria. Integrative therapies play a role in preventing the proliferation of pathogenic bacteria by supporting the

immune system rather than directly treating the infection. These approaches include different options such as probiotics, anti-inflammatory supplements, phytotherapies and immune boosters.

Inflammation during UTI can increase the severity of the infection and make the treatment process more difficult. Natural anti-inflammatories such as omega-3 fatty acids, turmeric (curcumin) and green tea polyphenols contribute to the healing process by reducing inflammation at the site of the infection. It is known that curcumin in particular can suppress the production of cytokines such as TNF-alpha and IL-6, which are the main components of inflammation (Carvalho, Fabio M., et al., 2021). Thanks to these properties, anti-inflammatory supplements can help the treatment process by controlling the spread of infection.

Cranberry is a herbal supplement frequently used to prevent urinary tract infections. Proanthocyanidins found in cranberry prevent *E. coli* from adhering to the bladder wall, reducing the risk of recurrence of infection (Sangeetha, Geminiganesan, and Ramesh Babu., 2022). Cranberry, which is especially effective against resistant *E. coli* strains, is considered as a preventive approach to antibiotic resistance.

Immune boosters such as vitamin C and zinc are effective in reducing the risk of infection by supporting the body's natural defense mechanisms. Vitamin C helps fight bacterial infections by increasing the phagocytic activity of neutrophils. At the same time, zinc is an essential mineral for the immune system and has the potential to reduce the risk of infection (Howell, Amy B., et al., 2024).

The results of this study highlight the challenges of antibiotic resistance in the treatment of urinary tract infections (UTIs) and the potential contribution of integrative treatment approaches to this process. While UTIs are particularly common among women, the increase in strains resistant to traditional antibiotic treatment complicates the management of infections. In this context, holistic approaches that aim to prevent recurrence of the disease rather than focusing solely on treating infections are gaining increasing importance (Ventola, C. Lee., 2015; McGuire, Shelley., 2016).

Integrative treatment methods can be evaluated both to shorten the treatment period and to prevent recurrent UTI cases. For example, the use of probiotics can prevent harmful bacteria from settling in the urinary tract, thus reducing antibiotic use. Studies on the protective effect of *Lactobacillus* species in UTIs reveal that probiotics can reduce the risk of infection by balancing the vaginal and urinary system flora (Stapleton, A. E., 2016). Such supportive treatments may reduce the need for antibiotic use by reducing the risk of infection.

The limited number of studies on the effectiveness of integrative treatment approaches in the management of UTIs indicates the need for more comprehensive research. Although early results from the studies are promising, the safety and efficacy of these treatments need to be confirmed in large-scale, randomized clinical trials (Gonzalez, Michael J., J. Miranda-Massari, and J. Rodriguez., 2020). More data are needed on how integrative treatment options can be used not only as

supportive therapy but also as preventive therapy to reduce the risk of infection. These studies should monitor the effects of integrative treatments in different patient populations and evaluate their long-term outcomes (Andersen, Marissa Jeme, et al., 2022).

Antibiotic stewardship programs need to be developed in the health sector to prevent unnecessary use of antibiotics. Antibiotic stewardship has the potential to reduce antibiotic resistance by preventing unnecessary antibiotic administration to patients. Increasing public awareness of rational antibiotic use and organizing public health campaigns on this issue can be an effective method to reduce antibiotic resistance. The World Health Organization (WHO) organizes global campaigns to raise awareness among health professionals and the public about the rational use of antibiotics. Such awareness campaigns are an important step towards preventing the spread of antibiotic resistance in society (Sami, H., Sultan, A., Rizvi, M., Khan, F., Ahmad, S., Shukla, I., et al., 2017).

As a result, antibiotic resistance poses a serious obstacle in the treatment of urinary tract infections and increases the importance of integrative treatment approaches. Probiotics, anti-inflammatory supplements, herbal supplements and immune system strengthening supplements can be considered as complementary treatment options in reducing the risk of recurrence of UTI. However, these treatment approaches need to be tested in more patient groups and their effects need to be monitored in the long term. Healthcare professionals' knowledge of these holistic approaches is considered an important step in the fight against antibiotic resistance.

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